

Abstract

Government policy frameworks contain important details that affect patterns in data on cease trade orders from the BC Securities Commission, as reported on SEDAR (2025). Specifically, failure to file a cease trade order (FFCTO) is a legal action by the BCSC that follows after a company misses a filing deadline. The FFCTO represents a critical government action to discipline so-called “reporting issuers” active in domestic capital markets, given their relatively large number of shareholders. This paper describes the basic methodology for measuring how promptly the government implements policy and illustrates the calculations using data.

Keywords: Capital Markets, Law, Halt, Cease Trade Order, Stranded Capital, Government Policy, Failure Rates

JEL Codes:

A1 - General Economics	Taxes and Subsidies
B4 - Economic Methodology	Policies
B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches	H57 - Procurement
C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation Methodology; Computer Programs	H8 - Miscellaneous Issues (352)
C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access	H82 - Governmental Property
D2 - Production and Organizations	K2 - Regulation and Business Law
D22 - Firm Behaviour Empirical Analysis	K22 - Business and Securities Law
D6 - Welfare Economics	K23 - Regulated Industries and Administrative Law
D62 - Externalities	K4 - Legal Procedure, the Legal System, and Illegal Behaviour
D8 - Information, Knowledge, and Uncertainty	L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy
D82 - Asymmetric and Private Information ; Mechanism Design	L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction
E3 - Prices, Business Fluctuations, and Cycles (2889)	P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform
E32 - Business Fluctuations ; Cycles	P16 - Political Economy
F6 - Economic Impacts of Globalization	Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and Conservation
G3 - Corporate Finance and Governance	Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development
H1 - Structure and Scope of Government	Q33 - Resource Booms
H2 - Taxation, Subsidies, and Revenue	
H23 - Externalities ; Redistributive Effects ; Environmental	

Methodology for Measuring Government Performance with Cease Trade Orders in BC 2019-2025

Government policy frameworks contain important details that affect statistical patterns, such as the time-series data on Cease Trade Orders from the BC Securities Commission (SEDAR, 2025). Specifically, failure to file a cease trade order (FFCTO) is a legal action the BCSC takes when a company misses a deadline to file required documents, such as financial statements. The FFCTO represents a critical government action to discipline so-called “reporting issuers”, which are companies that are active in capital markets based on their relatively large number of shareholders. This paper describes the basic methodology for measuring how promptly the government implements policy and illustrates the calculations using data from FFCTO in BC.

The baseline requirement for an FFCTO in BC is to start on the first day of the month. The reason is that government rules require documents to be filed on the last day of the month. If a company misses a deadline, then that causes an FFCTO. Can we measure the promptness of government policy by how close the issuance date is to the start of the month? It is not an exact measure, but a valuable exercise for identifying the target timeline between theory of policy and reality.

FFCTO should be issued to all at the start of the month. However, instances where this is not true can complicate things, because a management cease trade order can complicate things. Example of FFCTO that starts on a different date as follows. Suppose the BCSC issues a management cease trade order on the first day of the month after the company fails to file financial statements at the end of the prior month. The company negotiates with the BCSC for a management cease trade order lasting 2 weeks. After two weeks, the company fails to make the required disclosure, and the BCSC issues an FFCTO. In this case, the start of FFCTO is not on the first day of the month. Unclear how many data points like that are in the analysis here as undetected confounding variation.

Basic legal rules generate statistical patterns useful for exploratory data analysis. Collect all FFCTO from SEDAR (2025) for 2019 through 2025. Data for each FFCTO includes the date it was issued and its duration. Chart 1 compares the number of FFCTOs issued on each day of

the month across the entire sample set. Theoretically, most FFCTOs should be issued at the start of the month.

Chart 1: How many FFCTO were issued on each day of the month 2019-2025?

Note: Most FFCTO issued within first week of the month because financial statements always due last day of the month

As expected, the majority of all FFCTOs were issued in the first days of the month. This raises questions about the FFCTO issued after the 15th and whether the BCSC is slow to implement its own rules. For example, if a company failed to file at the end of the prior month and starts to trade heavily on the 15th of next month, then potential for market abuse, where someone transacts while they have material non-public information. Policy meant to protect investors. Essential to have consistent action on clear rules.

BCSC allows a company to continue issuing and trading securities, but insiders cannot transact. The reason is that the insiders have material non-public information regarding parts of the continuous disclosure requirements that the company failed to publish promptly. The company may have started with a “management cease trade order,” and the BCSC later changed to a full FFCTO, which means the FFCTO does not have to start on the first of the month.

Chart 2: Do the late-issued FFCTOs tend to have longer duration?

Note: uniform distribution for Duration of FFCTO (1-100) and for Day of Month when FFCTO issued (1-10)

Continue investigating the day of the month when FFCTO was issued. Any patterns for the duration of the FFCTO? Start by considering the duration of FFCTO to be only 1 day. Those quick FFCTO were generally issued in the first week of the month. Situations where the companies promptly address their delinquent filings and the BCSC quickly revokes the order. Both sides are working well where the government has clear rules and applies them consistently. Companies can understand rules and how to fix problems. Capital markets need to have clear, consistently applied rules so companies can plan and execute their strategies.

Chart 3 continues to investigate the day of the month when FFCTO was issued. Any patterns for the year when the FFCTO issued? Start by focusing on the FFCTO issued after the middle of the month because these represent instances where BCSC is relatively slow to issue orders. Appears that, in recent years, there has been more late-dated issuance of FFCTO. Is BCSC having problems keeping up with a larger number of FFCTO over time? Chart 4 shows a dramatic increase in the total number of FFCTO each year, doubling since 2019!

Chart 3: Has the BCSC started to issue more FFCTO later in recent years?

Note: Cluster of FFCTO issued in first days of the month for all years because financials always due last day of month

Chart 4: The total number of FFCTO has doubled from 30 in 2019 to 60 in 2024.

Note: More FFCTO Issued in recent years by BCSC

Chart 5A & 5B: Time Series of "Delay Score" for all FFCTO over time

Note: Introducing "Delay Score" to measure each FFCTO promptness relative to first day of the month

Note: the bounds here contain data 66% of the time

The toy model for “Delay Score” is calculated as follows ($\text{Score} = \text{Day} / 31 * 100$). It is designed to be an index number equal to 100 on the last day of the month, as a linear transformation of the number of days after the first of the month. The Delay Score measures the degree to which the FFCTO filing is late relative to the start of the month. The two versions, Chart 5A and 5B, show the same data, but 5B includes a non-parametric estimate of the moving average and error bounds over time. The data has been outside the bounds more often in recent years, as more frequent FFCTOs are issued overall and later each month. Do these patterns reflect delays at the BCSC in issuing FFCTO promptly?

To further improve this analysis, it is possible to refine the data assumptions to more accurately identify when FFCTOs were issued after management Cease Trade Orders. Can we identify companies that received FFCTO at later dates in the month for good reason, because of a management cease trade order? Can we otherwise explain why some FFCTOs were issued late in the month across the sample data set, based on the BCSC rules, or does it appear that the BCSC is sometimes very slow to implement its own rules? Do these periods in time when the BCSC is slower correspond to any other patterns in the market or other economic factors? How do we measure the costs and benefits of these FFCTO for capital markets, and can we measure any possible damages associated with the slow implementation of policy?

References

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